

Will 2025 witness another extensive mucilage outbreak in the Marmara Sea?

For people living around the Marmara Sea, which connects the Mediterranean Sea to the Black Sea (spanning 40°30'0" N to 41°00'00" N, 26°41'60" E to 30°00'00" E), spring 2021 was unusual due to a widespread mucilage event (Fig. 1a). Marine mucilage, also called sea snot, is composed of mucous aggregates exuded by some phytoplankton species, particularly the dinoflagellate *Gonyaulax fragilis* [1]. Mucilage presence was initially reported in the water column in the Dardanelles Strait (west of the Marmara Sea, Fig. 1a) from December 2020 to March 2021 [2]. Large surface aggregations were

also observed at this location in satellite imagery, starting in March 2021 (Fig. 1c), and later developed into a massive outbreak impacting the entire Marmara Sea (Fig. 1a). Satellite observations show peak mucilage abundance around 4 May 2021 (displayed in Fig. 1a; [3]), with the event ending in June.

The 2021 mucilage outbreak directly harmed the economy of Turkey (officially "Türkiye") due to travel cancellations impacting the tourism sector, which plays an important role in Turkey's GDP [4]. It also impacted fisheries [5], likely by causing enormous environmental damage such as oxidative

stress to seafood [6], or leading to mass mortality of benthic species [7] due to suffocation from mucilage (Fig. 2). Fish (particularly juveniles) also faced direct mass mortality resulting from the mucilage, with more than 10,000 individuals found dead over only four stations in the south of the Marmara Sea [8]. Although mucilage events also previously occurred in the Marmara Sea, notably in October 2007 and 2008, as well as in the adjacent Adriatic Sea ([9], submitted), the 2021 event represented a temporal (presence across ~three months) and a spatial (covered almost the entire region) record for the Marmara Sea [3].

For the current bloom, mucilage presence inside the water column was reported in December 2024 in the Dardanelles Strait (Fig. 3) and surface features were visible using satellite

Fig. 1. (a) MODIS-Aqua False-Red-Blue-Green (FRGB) image collected on 4 May 2021 showing presence of mucilage (white-yellow mesoscale slicks) across the entire Marmara Sea. (b) Inset highlighting the location of the Marmara Sea, between the Aegean Sea and Black Sea. (c) Sentinel-2 FRGB image collected on 28 March 2021 in the Dardanelles Strait (west of the Marmara Sea) showing surface aggregations of mucilage, two months before the outbreak displayed in (a). (d) Sentinel-2 FRGB image collected on 21 April 2025 in the Dardanelles Strait showing similar surface mucilage aggregations as panel (c).

Fig. 2. Mucilage covering the sea floor in the Aegean Sea, west of the Dardanelles Strait (near the city of Gökçeada, Turkey, 40°12'00" N, 25°53'60" E)], in February 2025. Images from <https://www.turkeyrecap.com/p/dawn-of-the-dead-zone-winter-mucilage>.

data covering the Strait in April 2025 (Fig. 1c). The reflectance spectral shapes of these features suggest that they are also caused by mucilage. Additional satellite data collected on 21 April 2025 (the same date as Fig. 1d) also show small mucilage features in the southeast of the Marmara Sea, near the city of Gemlik (Turkey, displayed on Fig. 1a). Do these observations precede another massive mucilage outbreak in the Marmara Sea in May–June 2025, similar to what happened in 2021? Will the delay in timing of the first surface aggregations (March in 2021, compared to April in 2025) also delay the potential outbreak to June – July, and might the environmental impacts (e.g., to juvenile fish populations) also differ as a result?

The specific conditions that cause *Gonyaulax fragilis*, or other potential mucilage producing species, to exudate large amounts of mucilage are unknown. Warmer temperatures in the region are believed to favor mucilage production [10], but additional factors may be required to precondition an outbreak. Indeed, relevant conditions leading to the mucilage outbreak in the northern Adriatic Sea during summer 2024 included elevated wintertime temperature, stratification, and subsequent nutrient influx from river discharge [11]. Whether or not the current mucilage presence is a harbinger of an eventual Marmara-wide outbreak during late Spring 2025 (mirroring the 2021 progression), this developing natural experiment offers the opportunity to monitor the event and collect key environmental

Fig. 3. In water mucilage aggregation in the Dardanelles Strait, picturing a diver surrounded by mucilage in December 2024. Image from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=akmwjqk96k4>.

variables. Such efforts may improve understanding of this phenomenon toward potential mitigation and remediation efforts.

References

1. Pistocchi R et al *Sci Total Environ* 353:307–316. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2005.09.087.
2. Özalp HB 2021 *J. Black Sea/ Mediterranean Environ* 27(1).
3. Hu C 2022. *IEEE Geosci Remote Sens. Lett* 19:1–5. doi: 10.1109/LGRS.2022.3173997.
4. Kalkavan C 2021. *J Black Sea/ Mediterranean Environ.* 27 (2), 258–269.
5. Karakulak FS, Kahraman AE, Uzer U, Gül B, Doğu S 2023. *Effects of mucilage on the fisheries in the Sea of Marmara Mucilage Probl. Sea Marmara Albay MED Istanbul Univ. Press Istanbul* 2:1–9. doi:10.26650/B/LS32.2023.003.09
6. Dagsuyu E et al 2025. *Environ Pollut* 374:126266. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2025.126266.
7. Özalp HB 2021. *J. Black Sea/Mediterranean Environ* 27(2):154–166.
8. Karadurmuş, Sari M 2022. *Turk J Zool* 46(1):93–102. doi: 10.3906/zoo-2108-14.
9. Hadjal M, Barnes BB, Qi L, Mikelsons K, Wang M, Hu C 2025. *Sci Total Environ.*
10. Kömüşçü AÜ, Aksoy A, Dogan OH 2022 *Int J Environ Geoinformatics* 9 (3). doi: 10.30897/ijegeo.1037842.
11. Vilibić I et al 2025. *Estuar Coast Shelf Sci* 317:109222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2025.109222>

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